

**D3.2 State of the art review and initial
design of 6G V2X/Digital Twin network
mechanisms**

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Acronyms

AD	Automated Driving
AI	Artificial Intelligence
CAM	Connected and Automated Mobility
CU	Central Unit
DaaS	Data as a Service
DT	Digital Twin
DU	Distributed Unit
GNN	Graph Neural Network
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
eNB	Evolved NodeB
IETF	Internet Engineering Task Force
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LSTM	Long short-term memory (LSTM)
MBMS	Multimedia Broadcast Multicast Service
ML	Machine Learning
MLB	Mobility Load Balancing
MNDT	Mobile Network Digital Twin
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
NDT	Network Digital Twin
NEF	Network Exposure Function
Near-RT	Near-real time
NF	Network Function
Non-RT	Non-real time
NWDAF	Network Data Analytics Function
OAM	Operations, Administration, and Maintenance
O-RAN	Open RAN
OWL	Web Ontology Language
PLMN	Public Land Mobile Network
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RRC	Radio Resource Control
RRM	Radio Resource Management
RTA	Road Traffic Authorities
RU	Radio Unit
SON	Self-Organized Network
ToD	Tele-operated Driving
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure
V2V	Vehicle-to-Vehicle
V2X	Vehicle-to-everything
V2X AF	V2X Application Function

Executive Summary

The characteristics of vehicular traffic create new challenges in the design of mobile communications systems that are normally designed for types of traffic like voice, video conferencing, gaming, streaming, etc. The vehicular traffic is very dynamic in nature and requires high reliability, which is related to the safety concerns in such services. Therefore, the current approach of network configuration via either manual setup of network configuration or self-organized network cannot cope with the complexity and dynamism of such traffic. Therefore, it is now obvious that artificial intelligence native networks are becoming a must to enable the deployment of such services.

The objectives of WP3 in UNICO 6GTWINROAD-MNO is to design an AI-native beyond 5G network based on the O-RAN architecture. In addition, the WP will also design and implement AI/ML algorithms exploiting historical and context information. To do so, new interfaces a generic historical information database will be designed and evaluated. The historical information database can be considered as a network digital twin including network configurations, relationships, and metrics that can reliability represent the network and allow the evaluation of AI/ML algorithms without risking the degradation of the network.

In this context, this deliverable reviews the state of the art related to network digital twin, AI native networks, and AI/ML-based algorithms for vehicular services. In addition, the deliverable also presents a preliminary architecture that can cope with the complexity of the vehicular traffic.

1 Introduction

One of the main enablers of the digital transformation and green policy is Connected and Automated Mobility (CAM) concept that relies on the existence of reliable and high-quality communications systems such as 5G and 6G networks.

Currently, there are two standardized technologies to provide CAM services or Vehicle-to-everything (V2X) communications: direct short-range communications (DSRC) technology [1]-[6] and Public Land Mobile Network (PLMN). DSRC supports V2X communications in the unlicensed band of 5.9 GHz using either IEEE 802.11p [1], IEEE 802.11bd [7], or using C-V2X [8], which is based on LTE and can operate without the presence of a Mobile Network Operator (MNO). In this respect, vehicles can communicate directly between them using Vehicle-to-Vehicle (V2V) communications or with roadside units using Vehicle-to-Infrastructure (V2I) communications deployed by Road Traffic Authorities (RTA). The V2I communication is essential in as they can improve the coverage in non-line of sight situations between vehicles such as intersection collision warning in urban areas. However, the need for RTA to massively deploy roadside units is a significant roadblock for the global adoption of such technology. Instead, PLMNs are already implemented and the benefit for Mobile Network Operators to continuously deploy more units is clear to enhance user experience and increase MNO revenues. Moreover, novel capabilities such as network slicing enables the creation of different independent virtual networks for vehicular services. In this context, 3GPP standard [9] defined a set of application enablers to ease the integration of V2X application functions with 5G networks [10]. Moreover, several 5G architectural enhancements such as both PC5 and Uu interfaces for implementing vehicular services were defined in [11]. Although not yet available in public networks, [11] also provided the capability of implementing Multimedia Broadcast Multicast Service (MBMS), which would lead to a more efficient radio resources usage in case of broadcast of groupcast communications.

However, large scale deployment of CAM services using PLMN (e.g., cooperative perception, autonomous driving, Tele-operated driving, and digital twins) are facing many challenges before becoming commercial reality. One aspect of these challenges is related to the high complexity of such services and their fast dynamism, which make any legacy planning unable to provide the required high reliability and Quality of Service (QoS). Therefore, integrated Artificial Intelligence (AI) in beyond 5G networks is a key design principle to enable CAM services. Therefore, the aim of 6GTWINROAD-MNO is to investigate and design an architecture for beyond 5G networks where AI is integrated in the control plane.

The 3GPP standard and difference alliances such as Open-Radio Access Network (O-RAN) alliance [12] have defined several architectural solutions to integrate AI concepts in communications systems. For instance, the 3GPP added the Network Data Analytics

Function (NWDAF) [13][14] to the core architecture. The NWDAF collects data from different sources, mainly the 5G core. It uses this data to provide powerful analytics supporting network self-organization and closed loop operations. The services of the NWDAF are exposed to external applications through the Network Exposure Function (NEF). Particularly, [10] described how the V2X Application Function (V2X AF) can manage interaction between the different users if the Uu interface is used and how the V2X AF interacts with the Network Exposure Function (NEF) and the NWDAF. Furthermore, the O-RAN alliance has defined a new flexible RAN architecture that allows the deployment of customized control plane functions, called xApps. The behaviour of the xApps is dictated by management applications, called rApps. The xApps and rApps can include AI algorithms for which data can be collected through the defined interfaces in the O-RAN architecture [15]-[17].

The main idea in 6GTWINROAD-MNO is to be able to build a *network digital twin* including the historical information collected information from the RAN, core, user equipment, and Operations, Administration, and Maintenance (OAM). The historical dataset will be used as inputs for AI/Machine Learning (ML) algorithms to optimize network performance and end user experience.

1.1 Deliverable overview

This deliverable is structured as follows. In Section 2, we present the state of the art related to network digital twins, AI native networks, and AI/ML-based algorithms for CAM services. In Section 3, we describe the motivation to design a new architecture that can be adapted to the complex and dynamic traffic generated by CAM services, and we discuss a preliminary architecture designed for that purpose. In Section 5, a summary of the topics discussed in the document will be provided.

2 State of the art

One of the emerging topics in the last couple of years is the digital twins for networks that can be used to optimize network performance and enhance end user experience. This can be done using an integrated AI in the control plane of mobile communications systems. In this section, we review the state of the art related to the creation of network digital twins, beyond 5G networks with integrated AI/ML frameworks, and AI/ML algorithms in the context of CAM service, especially for load balancing and predictive QoS.

2.1 Network digital twins

Digital Twin (DT) concept is becoming a key enabler for the digital transformation in many fields, e.g., CAM, industry 4.0, healthcare, aviation [18]. In addition, the concept of Network Digital Twin (NDT) or more precisely Mobile Network Digital Twin (MNDT) is also attracting the attention of researchers in the networking industry. The development of such NDT is becoming a reality due to the advances in computing power, modelling, and high-quality communications systems. The Internet Engineering Task Force (IETF) define an NDT as "an expansion platform of network emulation and can be seen as a tool for scenario planning, impact analysis, and change management" [19]. As noted in the draft, the main difference between NDT and a network simulator is the *interactive real-virtual mapping and data-driven approach* that enable the integration of closed-loop automation in next generation networks. The integration of NDT into the control plain of beyond 5G networks will allow assessing (AI-based) optimization frameworks in a risk-free environment. This will ensure the implementation of only the most effective changes in the real network. An NDT may involve five key elements (Figure 1): data, mapping, model, interface, and orchestration stack [20][21].

Figure 1 Key elements of network digital twin [10].

Data: A unified data repository collected from multiple network data sources. The data can be real time or historical data (topology data, configuration data, operational state data, trace data, KPI data) about the real physical network.

Data Model: An abstract model that organizes elements of data, e.g., YANG data models, database models, or knowledge graph.

Interface: Standardized interfaces used to ensure the interoperability of NDT. They interfaces can be split into two main types: telemetry interfaces between the NDT platform and the real network infrastructure, and Data as a Service (DaaS) interface between the NDT platform and external applications.

Mapping: It is used to provide real-time interactive mapping between the physical network and NDT, or between two different NDT.

Orchestration: Two types of orchestration are defined: one for the control of the NDT environment and its components to derive the required behaviour and the second is to deal with the dynamic lifecycle management of these components.

In [22], the authors propose an architecture of an NDT as an enabler for efficient network management and show its advantages in different domains such as network troubleshooting, what-if analysis, network planning, network anomaly detection, and education and training. The proposed architecture includes three elements: Digital Twin Network Model, Network Optimizer, and Training the Digital Twin. The Digital Twin Network Model is defined as a Blackbox containing ML-based network model. The authors argued that Graph Neural Networks (GNN) is the best technology that enables the construction of reliable NDT. The network optimizer is responsible for finding the best network configuration satisfying requirements set by the network operator. The obtained solution by the network optimizer is tried on the network model and if the output KPIs are not satisfactory the network optimizer will continue searching for a satisfactory configuration. The same approach of data collection is applied in [23] using an enrichment algorithm based on the semantic representation language Web Ontology Language (OWL), proposed by the World Wide Web Consortium (W3C) [24].

In [25], the authors show the importance of NDT in conjunction with AI to provide easy and cost-effective access to 5G networks. The authors in [26] develop a scalable NDT for network slicing, which aims at capturing the relationships between slices using a GNN model. Furthermore, the authors in [27] investigated the implementation of an NDT for optimizing the use of edge computing systems in 6G networks.

In addition to the architectural-related work presented above, some work has also been done on methodologies for modelling and implementing DTs [28][29].

The presented works above tackle the problem of creating and maintaining NDTs for generic 5G and beyond networks. However, the case of CAM services has some peculiarity due to the fast dynamics of such systems. In such scenarios, a combination

of NDT with DTs of the roads including the different vehicles will be necessary to model the real world where information can be exchanged between the beyond 5G network and the V2X applications, which are aware of vehicle and road -related information. By including such information, an AI-based framework can better optimize network configuration.

2.2 Mobile networks with integrated AI/ML

Although there is still no clear vision on what 6G networks will be, but there is a common agreement that AI will be a cornerstone of such networks. In this new vision, AI will not be any more isolated algorithms developed by network vendors for specific network problems, but it will be fully integrated in the system. Therefore, we are talking now about AI-Native 6G networks [30].

2.2.1 Autonomic system

The concept of intelligent networks is relatively old and first appeared as the concept of autonomic system that was defined by IBM as group of collaborative and interactive autonomic elements (See Figure 2). These elements alter their configurations to environmental changes in accordance with policies established higher architectural layers [31][32]. In autonomic systems, the autonomic element can perform a set of self-functions (e.g., self-configuration, self-optimization, and self-healing) in addition to self-knowledge ability.

Figure 2 Autonomic Element [32].

2.2.2 Self-Organized Network (SON)

The concept of autonomic systems was adopted by 3GPP standard for mobile communications and appeared first in the specifications of 4G networks under the name of Self-Organized Network (SON) [33]. The self-organization concept was applied to Evolved NodeBs (eNB) to support self-configuration and self-optimization functions. In this concept, the eNB can autonomously set some basic configurations when it is turned

on such as obtaining an IP address to communicate with the OAM, downloading necessary software and configuring its interfaces, configuring the neighbouring list, collecting information and KPIs, tuning radio parameters. The self-optimization procedures are usually closed loops that are performed repeatedly. Although the SON allowed the network operators to automatize some of the configuration and optimization tasks, the integrated algorithms were pre-defined generic algorithms developed to solve specific problems and could not adapt with the environment.

2.2.3 Network data analytics function (NWDAF)

In the last decade, the 3GPP also added intelligence to the core network in 5G systems through the integration of the NWDAF function [13][14]. The main purpose of the NWDAF is to generate network analytics reports, which can be used by other Network Functions (NFs) to make decisions. In the current specification, the NWDAF collect information from the OAM, but in practice several implementations allow the NWDAF to collect information from different core functions as in the case of Open Air Interface (OAI) implementation [34]. The NWDAF has two innovative concepts that were not available in the SON:

- Defining an intelligent function or engine that can autonomously collect and analyse data from different sources, and generate decisions related to network configuration, optimization, and healing,
- Expose the generated analytics to external applications through the NEF.

This latter functionality is crucial for 6G networks that are expected to serve different verticals (Industry 4.0, CAM, healthcare) with complex requirements that requires interaction between the network and the application servers.

2.2.4 O-RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC)

In the last decade, several research and alliances promoted the idea of open RAN to replace the monolithic all-in-one current RAN solutions. Although very performant, the legacy RAN solutions have many disadvantages such as limited configurability of the RAN, limited coordination between network elements necessary for joint optimization, and inter-operability problems between the solutions from different vendors [35]. In order to overcome these disadvantages, the O-RAN alliance [12] extended the concept of base station split in the 3GPP [36], where the base stations are split into Central Unit (CU), Distributed Unit (DU), and Radio Unit (RU). In the O-RAN architecture (See Figure 3, these units are connected to a RAN Intelligent Controller (RIC). The latter is responsible for controlling and managing the network at near-real time (near-RT) and non-real time (non-RT) scales.

Figure 3 O-RAN architecture [37].

The near-RT RIC is responsible for control loops on RAN nodes at the scale of 10 ms to 1 s. It resides in the edge of the mobile network and can interact with the RUs and Dus, in addition to O-RAN compliant LTE eNBs. Furthermore, it can be associated with several RAN nodes. The near-RT RIC encompasses a variety of supporting custom logic called x-Apps. Each xApp is a micro-service acts like a control loop performing radio resource management processes by collecting data from the RAN elements and, if necessary, make decisions that are send back to the RAN elements [38].

The non-RT time RIC complements the near-RT RIC for close loop operations on a time scale higher than 1 s. In addition, it supports the execution of third-party applications, called rApps. The latter are used to facilitate radio optimization and operations (e.g., policy guidance, enrichment information, configuration management, and data analytics) [35][39][40]. It should be noted that the behaviour of rApps can be customized based on policies dictated by the rApps

In addition to the fact that this architecture is dedicated to RAN, the main difference from the NWDAF is the more complex near-real time and non-real time algorithms that can be deployed in the RIC and change the configuration of the gNBs.

2.3 AI/ML-based algorithms for CAM services

Many Radio Resource Management (RRM) algorithms were proposed in the context of CAM services [41]. As mentioned in Deliverable D2.1 [44], two problems were selected to be evaluated in this project and the related SoA will be described in this section: Mobility load balancing and predictive QoS.

2.3.1 AI-based mobility load balancing algorithms

Mobility Load Balancing (MLB) has been a widely exploited topic over the last decades. However, the introduction of ML has constituted a big step for leveraging MLB algorithms, especially since traffic patterns on roads have shown to exhibit a strong periodicity [45]. These patterns can be exploited by data-driven techniques to maximize MLB efficiency. In particular, the high degree of flexibility of reinforcement learning (RL) algorithms makes them most suitable for MLB. Among the different RL techniques, Q-learning provides a robust performance in scenarios with a limited number of state variables and actions.

Q-learning algorithms were implemented to relieve cell overloads in an LTE scenario, either simulating pedestrian users with a network simulator [46] or generic hexagonal cell deployments [47]. More extensively, Q-learning was applied in [48] to optimize both mobile robustness optimization and MLB in the framework of SONs. Other works have focused on exploiting deep reinforcement learning as their state space was very large, either proposing centralized MLB solutions [49] or joint parameters optimization [50]. Moreover, algorithms such as double deep Q-networks or actor critic have been proposed, respectively, in [51] for jointly adapting the transmitting power and CIO, and in [50] for combining CIO and antenna tilt angle optimization. However, while the former considered a sub second timestep, which would introduce significant overhead on the amount of data traffic transmitted, the latter approximated all the cells to the same load regardless of the spectral efficiency.

Despite the wide literature of MLB in cellular networks, the amount of works in the scope of vehicular communications is limited. The authors of [52] proposed an MLB scheme in a vehicular network where users connected to their desired cell depending on the available QoS. User association was approached in [53] to balance loads in a multicell scenario by means of online reinforcement learning. Despite obtaining promising results, computing a global match for connecting individual users with all the cells compromised the flexibility of the presented solution. In [54], the authors propose a slice dimensioning algorithm based on reinforcement learning in presence of Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB) traffic considering a single-cell scenario. In [55], the authors analyse a large vehicular data set over an Italian highway. The analysis is used to develop a deep learning model to detect abnormal traffic situations (e.g. traffic jams), which then trigger the deployment of emergency network slices.

2.3.2 Predictive QoS for tele-operated driving

Safety in Tele-operated Driving (ToD) is crucial and can be significantly affected by sudden changes (especially degradation) in the provided QoS by the communication system. Therefore, tools and frameworks enabling the prediction of such changes can be game changer for ToD. For that reason, many research work and standard specifications proposed solutions for early notification about QoS changes.

The 3GPP has provided the *QoS sustainability analytics* service in the NWDAF [14], which notify the ToD application about predicted QoS change. The authors in [56] extend the 3GPP solution based on historical information. The data are collected from both OAM and Radio Resource Control (RRC) measurements and injected into a ML algorithm that is trained offline. When a QoS degradation is detected the ToD application is notified and the uplink quality of videos is reduced.

The authors of [57][58] study how QoS prediction can be used in different use cases of V2X communications. In [59], the authors devise a latency prediction model based on deep learning and passive probing for route selection of autonomous vehicles.

In [60], the authors propose a regression neural networks model in a federated learning fashion for estimating packet-based QoS metrics (latency and packet loss rate) derived from 5G network measurements in the context of V2X communication. The same approach of decentralized predictive QoS for V2X was proposed in [61] and they use their model to estimate the optimal level of compression to be used.

In [62], a recurrent neural networks model was proposed in order to predict QoS degradation for CAM applications. They design Long short-term memory (LSTM) network to identify patterns in network metrics and use it to predict QoS degradation.

3 Preliminary architecture

3.1 Motivation

In the current deployment of mobile networks (i.e., 4G and 5G), network configuration (e.g., neighbour cell list, handover parameter, load balancing and steering, PRB allocation for each network slice) is specifically tuned to cope with the requirements of the usual traffic (i.e., voice, web browsing, streaming, gaming) in a given area. Even implemented SON features are designed to cope with this type of traffic. However, the characteristics of traffic generated by the emerging services (e.g., CAM, healthcare, construction, industry 4.0) might require different configuration parameters than the current one. For instance, most of the emergent service requires more bandwidth in uplink than in downlink, which is not the case of current services. In addition, and more importantly, the dynamics in the traffic generated by these services is very high, is different in different cells, and require fast re-configuration and optimization of each cell separately. This will generate a problem of scalability in the existing model of implementing AI/ML (i.e., SON).

Furthermore, CAM services are still not yet commercially available despite the importance of such service, the interest of different stakeholders, and the creation of dedicated industrial alliance such as the 5GAA [63]. This is due to the inherent complexity of providing the necessary Quality of Service (QoS) in terms of reliability and availability needed to guarantee safety when using CAM services [64]. Therefore, AI/ML technology should be natively integrated in the control plane of mobile networks as it was done in the case of NWDAF and O-RAN RIC explained in Section 2.

One challenge appears when using the current implementation of the NWDAF (extracting data from OAM) is that the granularity with which data is obtained is of 15 minutes. Although this enables identifying different traffic mobility patterns, it is not sufficient for network reconfiguration when CAM services are connected due to their high dynamics. For instance:

- Traffic variation might be very fast. In this line, vehicular events such as traffic accidents will rapidly form an exacerbated increase of vehicular density and more vehicular services will need to be deployed around a particular area in few seconds.
- Failing at meeting V2X demanded QoS can lead to a service interruption, thus avoiding having cells overload is of key importance to deliver a successful service operation.

The 3GPP structure is not generally open to different actors to embed different application functions. In this line, the lack from an open ecosystem to adopt different applications may bound the benefits that can be delivered in vehicular scenarios.

3.2 Architecture

In order to overcome the main challenges explained above, we focus on the opportunities offered by the O-RAN architecture, which constitutes a versatile framework for building the next generation RAN as well as embedding support for AI/ML technologies. To this end, O-RAN defines the radio controllers where control functions at all network levels can be executed and the interfaces enabling the communication between them. Moreover, the high degree of openness enables embedding external application. In this regard we focus on using historical information, which is of key importance in vehicular environments, since the repeatability associated to vehicular mobility (such as daily commutes on weekdays or rest on weekends) can lead to a anticipate response to network resources demand increase. In this regard we consider obtaining different network indicators which provide sufficient insights on the challenges vehicular mobility poses in radio resources availability. Moreover, learning from previous experience can not only anticipate future overloads but illustrate which is the best way to mitigate them.

Although the interface does not exist, we propose an interface between the O-RAN and the NWDAF to enable V2X AFs to exploit the services provided by the proposed architecture. In Figure 4, we present the preliminary 6GTWINROAD-MNO architecture where we foresee the different vehicular services to be deployed. Among the different blocks, the green framed ones are the ones O-RAN architecture already supports. Then, the blue framed ones are already standardized by 3GPP on the 5G core. Finally, we add the usage of historical information to deliver an enhanced response to vehicular networks. The V2X AF can communicate directly with the NEF, or through an exposure interface (e.g. CAMARA API) that can hide the complexity of the core network interfaces. All interfaces are based on the standard except the two interfaces connecting the rApp to the NWDAF and the historical information database, which are proposed interfaces.

Figure 4 Preliminary 6GTWINROAD-MNO architecture.

In the digital twin for cooperative perception use case defined in Deliverable D2.1 [44], two xApps are defined and one rApp. The xApps are the KPI collection xApp that collects network KPIs with low granularity in the order of tens of milliseconds and the seconds runs the MLB algorithm. The rApp is the overload prediction rApp that decides based on real time KPIs and historical information the best action between three: Nothing, execute the MLB xApp, or notify the NWDAF about congestion when there is a congestion that cannot be solved with the MLB.

In this use case, the V2X AF subscribes through the NEF (or CAMARA) to an NWDAF congestion analytics service that will issue a notification when there is congestion in a geographic area. The congestion analytics module maps the geographical area to a set of cells and subscribes to the overload prediction rApp in the corresponding area for notification. Once the subscription is accepted by the rApp, the latter starts to monitor cell status and fetch the historical data to find similar patterns (See Figure 5). When found, the rApp checks the saved action (nothing, MLB, notify application) and acts upon that. If no similar pattern is found, an anomaly is detected and the rApp will execute MLB and if it does not give the required results, the NWDAF will be notified. In both cases, the action and the obtained result will be saved in the historical database together with the pattern. In case the V2X application is notified, it can take decisions related to the CAM application it runs. For instance, in case of tele-operated driving it can generate an alarm to the remote driver to reduce the speed or stop the vehicle. In case of cooperative perception, the frequency of cooperative awareness messages can be reduced in a smart way (e.g., reduce only the frequency of stopped vehicles on a traffic light).

Figure 5 Procedure followed by the proposed solution.

The use of historical information will enable the rApp to save the time of MLB execution that can be long in case AI algorithms are running. In fact, the analysis of the data provided in Deliverable D3.1 [65] showed highly periodical patterns in the different KPIs over all cells and during the two months of data collection. As it can be seen in Figure 6, the repeated pattern is obvious. AI/ML algorithms can be easily designed to predict the future behaviour of such KPI.

Figure 6 Variation of the traffic during the month of September in a 5G cell.

The historical information database acts as a network digital twin as it contains all the needed information to evaluate AI/ML algorithms without trying them on the operational network and risk breaking the network. It should be noted that while the MLB solution is ideal in scenarios where resources demand can be alleviated by diverting furthestmost users to a neighbouring cell. Alternatively, we decrease the V2X messages of vehicles.

4 Conclusions

In this document, we highlighted the need for a new architecture where the AI is fully integrated in order to adapt to the highly exigent traffic generated by vehicular applications. We also discussed the state of the art related to network digital twins, AI native networks, and AI/ML-based algorithms for CAM services. Based on the analysis of the state of the art, we also introduced a preliminary architecture for an AI native beyond 5G network.

The proposed architecture relies on the combination of NWDAF and O-RAN frameworks, in addition to the key element which is the historical information database that allows the AI models to identify patterns in the different network metrics and take efficient decisions accordingly.

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